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AN APPRAISAL OF THE APPLICATION OF THE AFRICAN CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY, ELECTIONS AND GOVERNANCE IN NIGERIA

By

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ABSTRACT

The involvement of people of a state or polity in decision making and the state of affairs of a Government is the unique feature of democracy. The African Union (AU) joined the international community in recognizing democracy as the most acceptable system of government and thus, in 2007 adopted the African Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance. Prior to the inception of the charter on democracy, Nigeria has been operating democratic governance since 1999. However, corruption, insincerity of purpose and lack of accountability characterize most of the Nigerian political leaders. Political parties which are among the key players in smooth conduct of democratic elections in Nigeria are in most cases undemocratic in their nominations of candidates due to the lack of proper monitoring by the electoral body (INEC) whose independence is also not absolute. Now that Nigeria has signed and ratified the Charter on Democracy, the objective of this paper is to examine the roles of various democratic institutions and stakeholders whose role is paramount in the conduct of Democratic Elections in Nigeria with a view to determine whether or not they are in consonance with the Charter on Democracy. The final objective of the paper is to evaluate the performance of Nigerian democratic government in the promotion of Elections and to suggest other possible ways of promoting good governance. The research is doctrinal and therefore documented sources were consulted and analyzed. Previous authors in the area have attempted to discuss democratic elections and constitutional democracy in Nigeria. However, the topic of democratic elections in Nigeria under the Charter on Democracy was not

addressed satisfactorily. Therefore, this paper aimed to bridge this gap in order to accomplish the previously mentioned objectives. The research found that provisions of the Charter on Democracy will bring about peace and political stability in Africa. It has also found that the independence of the electoral body (INEC) in Nigeria is not absolute regarding its funding and appointment of its chairman. It was finally found that internal democracy is missing in most of the political parties in Nigeria when it comes to nomination of candidate that will be a flag bearer in general elections. It is recommended that Nigeria being a state party to the Charter on Democracy should domesticate and implement its provision with view to having peace and political stability. INEC should have absolute independence in all regards particularly in relation to its funding. It should properly monitor the activities of political parties to avoid votes buying and other anti-democratic practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

Elections are central institutions of democratic representative governments. In democracy, the authority of the government is derived solely from the consent of the people. The principal mechanism for translating that consent into government authority is the holding of free and fair election.¹ To this end, African Union (A.U)² in 2007 adopted the African Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance³ with the hope of promoting democratic system of government at the continental and/or regional level.

A free and fair election can only be actualized where the electoral body is independent, impartial and incorruptible in the conduct and management of elections. Political parties play an important role in democratic election. Unless internal democracy within political Parties is well established, they can hardly sponsor a good candidate that represents the general interest of the people when elected as a political office holder.

The Charter on Democracy which one of its objectives is to provide enabling environment that allows Africans to participate in the choice of their leaders through periodic elections, frowns at unconstitutional change of government that has being the major cause of insecurity in African polity. Nigeria as a member of the AU has been operating democratic system of government since 1999. However, in Nigeria many instances reveal that the General elections

¹www.usa.usem.bassy. Accessed on 10/11/2017

² Hereinafter referred as the AU

³ Hereinafter referred to as the Charter on Democracy

which ought to be a means of actualizing citizens' right to vote turned to be a threat to their rights to life and personal liberty mostly resulting from election malpractices due to lack of a true independent electoral body. Participation in Elections in Nigeria has become a lucrative business where politicians or political parties spend much of their monies in vote buying at primaries and general elections with the aim of making more profits when they assume political leadership.

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEMS

Nigeria has been operating democratic governance since 1999 to date. However, corruption, insincerity of purpose and lack of accountability characterize most of the Nigerian political leaders and Institutions. The paper has the following statement of problem:

Political parties which are among the key players in smooth conduct of democratic elections in Nigeria are in most cases undemocratic in their nominations of candidates due to the lack of proper monitoring by electoral body (INEC).

The independence of INEC is not absolute as its funding for the conduct of elections is coming from executive arm. The Charter on Democracy adopted by AU in 2007 has been signed and ratified in 2012 by Nigeria but not yet domesticated to enable it gain enforceability in our domestic courts. It is against the above backdrop that the research addressed these problems and provided necessary recommendations to the various stakeholders involved in the promotion of democratic elections and governance via appraisal of Domestic Implementation of African Charter on Democracy, Elections and Governance in Nigeria

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objective of this paper is to examine the roles of various democratic institutions and stakeholders whose role is paramount in the conduct of Democratic Elections in Nigeria With the aim of determining whether they are in accordance with the Charter on Democracy. The final objective of the paper is to evaluate the performance of Nigerian democratic government in the promotion of Elections and to suggest other possible ways of promoting good governance. The paper would thus analyze elections in Nigeria under the Charter on Democracy to accomplish the objectives mentioned earlier.

Research Methodology

The methodology adopted in the research is doctrinal where documented sources were consulted. For instance, in this research substantive and case laws were referred to; both local and foreign. Literatures of legal experts like textbooks and articles in journals were also consulted. All sources were duly acknowledged.

4. CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS

4.1 DEMOCRACY

Article 4 paragraphs 1 of the Charter on Democracy provides that: “State parties shall commit themselves to promote Democracy..., ”⁴. The Charter on Democracy obliges its state parties to commit themselves to promote Democracy which is the government put in place by the people, which upholds the spirit of social contract between the state and the people, ensures equitable distribution of the state resources and equal opportunity for all its citizens, and whose operations are based on the rule of law.⁵ The government must be characterized by the involvement of the people (citizens) in the choice of their leaders, supremacy of the law, equality of all citizens before the law, personal liberty, among others.

The concept of democracy is traceable to the ancient Greeks and specifically the city-state of Athens in the fifth century B.C. The word democracy is derived from the Greeks word ‘*demos*’ meaning people and ‘*kratos*’ meaning power or rule. Directly translated, the word Democracy means ‘rule by the people’. Originally they used it to mean the poor or the masses.⁶ In 1863, Abraham Lincoln, the President of the United States of American who led the war against slavery, defined democracy as “government of the people, by the people, for the people”.⁷ This is probably the most frequently used definition of democracy. People raffle it off almost automatically, without pondering its deeper significance. Lincoln’s definition emphasizes the government. But in its root meaning, is first and foremost about “the people” not government. In today’s world, government is often the center of the action. Democracy therefore according to Idike,⁸ is a political system in which the people in the country rule through any form of government they choose to establish. Democracy is not governed by the elite, even though the

4 Article 4, Paragraph 1 of the Charter on Democracy

5Nwekeaku, C. (2014) *The Rule of Law, Democracy and Good Governance in Nigeria*, www.ea-journals.org-accessed on 23/12/2016

6Arat, Z. F,(1991), *Democracy and Human Rights in Developing Countries*, Lynne Rienner Publisher Inc., London, p. 15.

7Lincoln. history.illinois.edu, accessed, 14/11/16; 8:30pm

8Idike, A.A *Democracy and Electoral Process in Nigeria: Problems of E. Voting Option*, www.ajuss.org., accessed 14/11/2016.

representatives elected by popular vote form part of the political elite. Democracy is primarily governed by the representatives of the people without discrimination. the core of the concept and practice of democracy, are the desires and the will of the people.

4.2 ELECTIONS

To elect simply means “to choose or make a decision” the simple definition of election is the act or process of choosing someone for a public office by voting. Election is a formal decision making process by which a population chooses an individual to hold public office. Elections have been the usual mechanism by which modern representative democracy has operated since 17th century. Elections may fill offices in the legislature and executive.⁹

The universal use of elections as a tool for selecting representatives is in contrast with the practice in the democratic archetype, ancient Athens, where the elections were considered an oligarchic institution and most political offices were filled using sortation also known as allotment, by which office holders were chosen by lot. Other forms of ballot such as referendums are referred to as elections especially in the United States.¹⁰ The concept of election has been earlier on defined in this work, since in a democracy the ideal is seeking the consent and mandate of the citizens for any leader to be accepted as legitimate, citizen participation in the choice of their leaders is important.

4.3 GOOD GOVERNANCE

The concepts of Governance and good governance are being increasingly used in the recent times in development literature. Scholars and institutions alike advanced different definitions of governance. For instance, United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia¹¹ defined governance as “the process of decision making and the process by which decisions are implemented involving both the formal and informal actors”. It was also asserted that good governance depends on the extent to which it is participatory, consensus oriented, transparent and accountable. The term good governance focuses in the responsibility of government and governing bodies in meeting the needs of the governed. Its basic principles of selflessness,

9Mafuyi, M. W (2015) The Rule of Law and the Challenges of Electoral Process in Nigeria, *B.U.K Journal of International Law and Jurisprudence*, Vol. 1 No. 1

10Klein, A. *Concepts and Principles of Democratic Governance and Accountability*. www.kas.de/.../kas-29779-1522-2-30.pdf..., accessed, 2/12/2016.

11 Here in after referred to as UNESCAP 2010

objectives, integrity, accountability, openness, or transparency and leadership are well established¹².

Good Governance is the process whereby public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources and guarantee the realization of human rights in a manner essentially free of abuse and corruption and respectful of the rule of law.¹³ Therefore, good governance can be said to be the observance of rule of law and a just management of public resources by institutions of government.

5.0 THE CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY AND DEMOCRATIC ELECTIONS IN NIGERIA

Elections are central institutions of democratic representative governments. In a democracy, the authority of the government is derived solely from the consent of the people. The principal mechanism for translating that consent into government authority is the holding of a free and fair election.¹⁴ All modern democracies hold elections but not all elections are democratic. Jeane Kirkpatrick, a scholar and former U.S ambassador to the United Nations defines Democratic Elections as “the elections that are competitive, periodic, inclusive, definitive election in which the chief decision-makers in government are selected by citizens who enjoy broad freedom to criticize government, to publish their criticism and present alternative”¹⁵

The Charter on Democracy therefore, encourages state parties relating to elections to:

“...re-affirm their commitment to regularly holding transparent, free and fair elections in accordance with African Union’s Declaration on the principles governing democratic election in Africa.”¹⁶

To this end state parties shall:

12 Bappah A.A (2015) The Application of the Rule of Law, Democracy and Good Governance in Nigeria Challenges and Prospects. In Danladi K. M (ed) *Law Making, Challenges and Good Governance in Katsina State*, Clear Resolution, Abuja,(2015) p. 11-12

13 Ibid

14 www.usa.usem.bassy. Accessed on 10/11/2017

15 Ibid

16 Article 17 of the Charter on Democracy

1. Establish and strengthen independent and impartial national electoral bodies responsible for the management of the election.
2. Establish and strengthen national mechanisms that redress election related disputes in a timely manner.
3. Ensure fair and equitable access by contesting parties and candidates to state controlled media during elections.
4. Ensure that there is binding code of conduct governing legally recognized political stakeholders, government and other political actors prior, during and after elections. The code shall include a commitment by political stakeholders to accept the results of the elections or challenge them through exclusively legal channels.¹⁷

The interrelationships between and among the right to genuine elections and other internationally recognized civil and political rights illustrates that democratic elections must be inclusive both for citizens who want to exercise their right to vote and for those who seek to be elected. An anti-discrimination norm obliges states to provide inclusiveness in electoral processes.¹⁸ The norm against discrimination takes the force of a principle for democratic elections as the requirements for universal and equal suffrage combine with the general prohibition against discrimination, the rights to equality before the law and equal protection of the law and the right to remedies that effectively redress rights violations.¹⁹ Provisions concerning all of these concepts are found in the Charter on Democracy. In line with the previously mentioned provisions, the following bodies were established for management of elections and election disputes resolution in Nigeria.

17 Ibid

18 Patric, M. (2008) Promoting Legal Framework for Democratic Elections, National Democratic Institute for International Affairs, Washington, www. Eods.eu. accessed on 25/8/2018

19 Ibid

5.1 INDEPENDENT NATIONAL ELECTORAL COMMISSION (INEC)

The Independent National Electoral Commission is the mechanism put in place by Nigerian Constitution for the smooth conduct and entronement of political leaders through periodic elections.²⁰ This is in line with article 17 paragraph 1 of the Charter which provides that “States Parties shall establish and strengthen independent and impartial national electoral bodies responsible for the management of elections”²¹The independence of the electoral body must be a reality not only in name. Therefore, INEC in Nigeria must be seen as independent of partisan bias or control, even of the incumbent administration. This relates to the selection of its members, the autonomy of its budget and the authority it exerts to enforce the election laws and regulations. The system for counting and aggregation of votes must be made more transparent and verifiable. There must be evidence of prosecution of violators. A climate of impunity will undo the best rules or regulations.²²

The INEC is made-up of the Chairman, 12 Commissioners at the federal level and a Resident Electoral Commissioner for each state of the federation and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.²³ The appointment of the INEC Chairman and its members is to be made by the President subject to the confirmation by the Senate.²⁴ INEC has also been classified by the Constitution as a Federal Executive Body.²⁵ This brings it under the over sight of the executive arm of government. Unlike the funding of the Judiciary, the funds needed for elections and running of the commission are not charged on the consolidated fund. The INEC has to submit its budget to the executive for approval after which they are passed with the national budget.²⁶ Therefore, Nigeria being a state party to the Charter on Democracy even though did not domesticate it, but to show its commitment, there is need to amend its national laws to make INEC truly independent in all aspect. However, it will be most desirable if the Charter on Democracy will be domesticated so that it can be enforceable in our local courts.

20 S. 153(1) of the Constitution

21 Article 17 para. one of the Charter

22 Frances, O.I. (2013). *The Role of INEC in Fostering Good Governance*. In: Azinge, E. and Adediran A. (eds) *Legislating for Good Governance*, NIALS Press, Abuja. P. 278

23 S. 14(1) and (2) Third Schedule, pt. 1 of the Constitution

24 S. 154(1) of the Constitution

25 S. 153 of the Constitution

26 Frances, O.I. (2013). *The Role of INEC in Fostering Good Governance*. In: Azinge E. and Adediran A. (eds) *Op. Cit.* P.278

INEC as the electoral body vested with the duty of ensuring that elections are conducted as at when due, has a major role to play before, during and after the elections. Some of these duties provided by the Constitution include: -

1. Organize, undertake and supervise all elections to the office of the president and vice-president, the governor and deputy governor of a state, and the membership of the senate, the House of Representatives and the House of Assembly of each state of the federation.
2. Register political parties in accordance with provision of the Constitution and an Act of National Assembly.
3. Monitor the organization and operation of the political parties including their finances.
4. Arrange for the annual examination and auditing of all funds and accounts of political parties and publish a report on such an examination and audit for public information.
5. Arrange and conduct the registration of persons qualified to vote and prepare, maintain and revise the register of voters for the purpose of any election under this constitution.
6. Monitor political campaigns and provide rules and regulations which shall govern the political parties.
7. Ensure that all electoral commissioners, electoral and returning officers take and subscribe the oath of office prescribed by law.
8. Delegate any of its powers to any Resident Electoral Commissioner and carry out such other functions as may be conferred upon it by an Act of the National Assembly.²⁷

The roles of INEC in promoting the legitimacy of elections by reducing political corruption is further elaborated by the Electoral Act 2010 which states that INEC shall have power to:- “(a) Conduct voter and civic education, (b) Promote knowledge of sound democratic election processes and (c) Conduct any referendum required to be conducted pursuant to the provision of the 1999 Constitution or any other Law or Act of the National Assembly.”²⁸ The above provisions of the Constitution and Electoral Act are all meant to protect the integrity of the

27 S. 15(a-i) 3rd Schedule, pt 1 of the Constitution
28 S. 2, Electoral Act, 2010

electoral body in Nigeria (INEC) with the aim of achieving a free and fair election which end is having competent, credible and responsible persons as leaders of the country who ensure good governance and development.

For democracy to be given life, people must participate. Political parties play a critical role in the participating process, providing the main organizational link between Politicians who run for office and the general public. To this end, the Charter on Democracy obliged State party to provide means of “Strengthening political pluralism and recognizing the role, rights and responsibilities of legally recognized constituted political parties, including opposition political parties, which should be given a status under national law.”²⁹ In compliance with the aforementioned Article, INEC in Nigeria has been empowered to register any political party that satisfied the requirements of the law. The Electoral Act provides that:

Any political association that complies with the provision of the Constitution and this Act for the purpose of registration shall be registered as a political party. Provided however, that such application for registration as a political party shall be duly submitted to the Commission not later than 6 months before a general election.³⁰

In Nigeria only the candidates who are sponsored by a political parties recognized by INEC can contest into an election.³¹ In most democracies, the link provided by political parties may be indirect at best. Usually the public has very little connection with parties except on election days, internal party affairs tend to be controlled by professional politicians and their staff or through delegate system in some of the political parties.³² However, some parties in the democratic world allow its members to take part in meetings to discuss policy, issues and perhaps votes for the party’s top leader or its candidates for office. Such parties provide a space for political participation by ordinary citizens at the grass root level.³³ Thus parties remain indispensable to democracy because they enable citizens to play a role in policy making and are then principal means for the representation of the electorate in both national and local

29 Article 3, Para. 11 of the Charter on Democracy

30 S. 78(1), Electoral Act, 2010

31 S. 31, Ibid.; *Amaechi v. INEC* (2008) ALL FWLR pt 407

32 See for example, s. 33(1), Constitution of People Democratic Party (As amended in 2012) where it itemized the class of people eligible to participate at National Convention of the party.

33 Bappah, A.I (2015), *The Application of the Rule of law, Democracy and Good Governance in Nigeria Challenges and Prospects*. In Danladi K. M (ed) *Law Making, Challenges and Good Governance in Katsina State*, Clear Resolution, Abuja, p. 9

government.³⁴ Political parties therefore, facilitate governance by bringing order to the process of policy making. Party's members, individual politicians have an existing group of allies that usually cooperate with their efforts to enact and implement legislations. More so, party alliances close the gap between the legislature and other branches of government.

5.2 ELECTION COURTS OR TRIBUNAL

The Charter on Democracy under Article 17 paragraph 2 obliges the state parties to “establish and strengthen national mechanism that redress election related disputes in timely manner.”³⁵

Regarding elections' disputes resolution in Nigeria, the electoral Act provides that:

No election and return at an election under the Electoral Act shall be questioned in any manner other than by a petition complaining of an undue election or undue return presented to the competent Tribunal or Court in accordance with the Constitution or Electoral Act, and in which the person elected or returned is joined as a party.³⁶

The Tribunal or Court means Court of Appeal in case of Presidential election and election Tribunal established under the Constitution or Electoral Act in the case of any other election.³⁷

The election tribunals shall be constituted not later than 14 days before the election and when constituted open their registries for business 7 days before the election.³⁸

The Courts with original jurisdiction to hear and determine election dispute in Nigeria are:

The Court of Appeal shall to the exclusion of any other court of law in Nigeria, have original jurisdiction to hear and determine any question to whether:

34Anele, k. k. (2013) Political Party Ideology and Legislation for Good Governance. In: Azinge, E. and Adediran, A. (eds). *Legislating for Good Governance*, NIALS Press, Abuja. P. 239

35 Article 17 paragraph two of the Charter on Democracy

36 S. 133(1), Electoral Act, 2010

37 S. 133(2), Ibid

38 S. 133(3), Ibid

Any person has been validly elected to the office of president or vice president under the Constitution or The term of office of the president or vice president has ceased or that office becomes vacant.³⁹

The Constitution also establishes National and State House of Assembly Election Tribunals for each state of the federation and Federal Capital Territory Abuja and Governorship Election Tribunal. It provides thus:

There shall be established for each state of the federation and Federal Capital Territory Abuja one or more election tribunals to be known as the National and State House of Assembly Election Tribunals which shall to the exclusion of any other court or tribunal have original jurisdiction to hear and determine petitions as to whether:

1. Any person has been validly elected as a member of the National Assembly or
2. Any person has been validly elected as a member of the State House of Assembly of a state.⁴⁰

The Constitution also provides thus:

There shall be established in each state of the federation an Election Tribunal known as Governorship Election Tribunal which to the exclusion of any other court or tribunal shall have original jurisdiction to hear and determine petitions as to whether any person has been validly elected to the office of Governor or Deputy Governor of a state.⁴¹

The Constitution vested jurisdiction in the Court of Appeal in Nigeria to hear and determine appeal on election matters where it provides that: “The Court of Appeal has power to hear and determine appeal from decisions of the National and State Houses of Assembly Election Tribunal and decision of the Governorship Election Tribunals.”⁴²

The Supreme Court of Nigeria has power to hear appeal as to whether any person has been:

39 S. 239 of the Constitution
40 S. 285(1) Ibid
41 S. 285(2) Ibid
42 S. 246(2) b and c Ibid

- i. Validly elected to the office of the President or Vice President
- ii. Whether the term of office of President or Vice President has ceased or his office has become vacant.
- iii. Whether any person has been validly elected to the office of Governor or Deputy Governor or his term of office ceased or his office becomes vacant under the Constitution.⁴³

The above courts are recognized by the Constitution to resolve election matters. Other courts may also be established to resolve election matters. For examples the Electoral Act of 2010 provides that:

There shall be established for the Federal Capital Territory one or more Election Tribunal which shall to the exclusion of any other court or tribunal have original jurisdiction to hear and determine any question as to whether:

Any person has been validly elected to the office of Chairman, vice chairman or councilor, or their term of office ceased or the seat of a member of an Area Council has become vacant.⁴⁴

The above provisions of Constitution and the Electoral Act 2010 are meant to ensure that there is a binding code of conduct and laws governing legally recognized political stakeholders, government and other political actors prior, during and after elections. And those political stakeholders are to accept the results of election or challenge them through exclusively legal channels in line with requirements of the Charter on Democracy.⁴⁵ For example, in the case of *Amaechi v INEC*,⁴⁶ the Supreme Court of Nigeria held that the substitution of *Omehia* for *Ameachi* was not done in accordance with law and consequently he was the candidate of the People's Democratic Party (PDP) for whom the party campaigned in the April 2007 election and since PDP was declared to have won the said election *Amaechi* must be deemed the candidate that won the election for the PDP. In the eyes of law, *Omehia* was never a candidate in the election much less the winner. Also in *Peter Obi v INEC*⁴⁷ the Supreme Court of the

43 S. 246(1) b and c Ibid

44S. 135(1), *Electoral Act*, 2010

45 Article 17 para. 4 of the Charter on Democracy

46 (2008)ALL FWLR pt 407

47 (2007)11 NWLR pt1046

land held that with reference to sections 184 and 285 of the Constitution that the four years term of office of the plaintiff commenced on 17/3/2006 when he first took the oath of office. His term will not expire until 17/3/2010.

5.3 MEDIA, NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL OBSERVERS

Transparency is an essential attribute of democratic Elections. The media plays an important role in making elections more transparent. In order to ensure freedom of expression and equality before the law of all legally recognized political parties, the Charter on Democracy obliges the state parties to “ensure fair and equitable access by contesting parties and candidates to state controlled media during elections.”⁴⁸ While seeking the establishment or strengthening of national electoral bodies, mechanisms to settle contested elections, free and equal access for all candidates to media outlets, and a code to govern the conduct of elections, including processes for post-election issue.⁴⁹ This can be found also in Nigeria under section 39 of the Constitution which provides for the freedom of expression and the press.

The Charter on Democracy obliges the “state parties to inform the African Union Commission of scheduled elections and invite it to send an electoral observer mission. The state party shall guarantee conditions of security, free access to information, non–interference, freedom of movement and full cooperation with the electoral observer mission.”⁵⁰ It also provides that “State parties shall create conducive environment for independent and impartial national monitoring or observation mechanisms.”⁵¹

To ensure security before, during and after election, the Charter on Democracy obliged state parties before the commencement of each election, “... to negotiate with legally recognized political parties and other political players about adopting a code of conduct by means of which they will promise to accept the result of the election or contest them by exclusively legal means.”⁵² The participation of African Union (AU) in the electoral process is done through the Department of Political Affairs of the Commission. The state parties are to inform the executive body of AU about the date of the election and to invite them to send observer mission to that

48 Article 17 para 3 of the Charter on Democracy

49 Glean, P. J (2012) *Institutionalizing Democracy in Africa: A Comment on the African Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance*, African Journal of Legal Studies, www.bril.nl/ajls. Accessed on 22/1/2018

50 Article 19 of the Charter on Democracy

51 Article 22 Ibid

52 Article 17 para 4 Ibid

country. Once the invitation is accepted, a memorandum of understanding is signed with the AU Commission in accordance with its principles and relevant laws of the host state.⁵³

The Department of Political Affairs must place the necessary materials and human means for their proper management at the disposal of the observation mission. In particular, it must ensure that the electoral battles are conducted in an objective, impartial and transparent manner. At the end of the observation mission, draws up a report which it submits to the chairman of the Commission within a reasonable period. The Chairman also prepares a report on the election and the following activities suggested by the observer mission which is then communicated to the member states of the AU and made public.⁵⁴ The Charter on Democracy also obliges the state parties to allow independent and impartial national monitoring or observation mechanism. This gives room to Non-Governmental Organizations and other civil societies to participate in the observation and monitoring of an election.

6.0 ISSUES RELATING TO THE APPLICATION OF THE CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY IN NIGERIA

Nigeria has been a very active member of the international community since gaining independence and joining the United Nations in October, 1960. Thus, Nigeria remains active within the United Nations and African Union system and demonstrated commitment to and acceptance of the International and Regional political and legal system embodied in various universal multilateral treaties, conventions and charters instituted under the guidance of the United Nations and African Union.⁵⁵

In Nigeria, mere signing an international instrument by the President or his representative does not make it enforceable in Nigerian courts. The treaty or international instrument must first be domesticated to be part of municipal law. The laws governing domestication and implementation are provided under the Constitution and Treaties (Making Procedure etc.) Act.⁵⁶

53 Sakai, I.(2007). *A Critical Look at the Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance*, www.sarpn.org. Accessed 25/10/2017

54 Ibid

55 Aliyu, A. (2016) *The Challenges of Implementing International Treaties in Third world Countries: The case of Maritime and Environmental Treaties Implementation in Nigeria*. www.iiste.org. Accessed on 21/1/2018

56 Cap. T16 LFN 2004

The Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as Amended addressed the issue of treaty making and its implementation under section 12 of the Constitution. The section provides thus:

- 1 No treaty between the federal and any other country shall have the force of Law except to the extent to when any such treaty has been enacted into law by the National Assembly.
- 2 The National Assembly may make law for the federation or any part thereof with respect to matter not included in the executive legislature list for the purpose of implementing a treaty.
- 3 A bill for an act of the National Assembly passed pursuant to the provision of subsection (2) of this section shall not be presented to the president for assent, and shall not be enacted unless it is ratified by a majority in the federation.⁵⁷

Nigeria is a state party to the African Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance as she signed and ratified it and deposited her instrument for ratification with Chairperson of African Union on 9th January, 2012, which makes Nigeria bound by provisions of the Charter on Democracy.⁵⁸ Therefore notwithstanding, the Constitutional provision requires for domestication of a treaty before it can become enforceable in the Nigerian courts. At the international level, Nigeria is under obligation to perform its duties in accordance with provisions of the Charter on Democracy following its ratification. Article 26 of Vienna Convention on the Laws of Treaties is to that effect.⁵⁹ The Vienna Convention on the Laws of Treaties also provides that: “Once a Country adopted a treaty or charter it cannot also rely on any of its domestic law to go contrary to the provisions of the treaty or the charter.”⁶⁰ The Nigerian Courts provide many decisions on relationships between treaty or charter and Nigerian Law. In *Oshevire v. British Caledonia Airways Ltd.*⁶¹ Ogundere JCA held that “...any domestic legislation in conflict with the convention is void.” The implication of this decision is that such a convention or treaty is treated higher in status than a municipal legislation. This issue also came before Supreme Court of Nigeria for examination in the case of *Fawehimi v.*

57 S. 12 of the Constitution

58 www.au.org. Accessed on 18/3/2018

59 Article 26, Vienna Convention on Laws of Treaties 1969

60 Article 27 Ibid

61 (1990) FWLR (pt 163) p.507 at 519 - 520

Abacha.⁶² In that case the applicant (Chief Gani Fawehimi) a legal practitioner was arrested without warrant at his residence by men of the State Security Service (SSS) and policemen. He sought to enforce his fundamental rights pursuant to the Fundamental Rights (Enforcement Procedure) Rules 1979 and in accordance with Articles 4, 5 and 12 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act.⁶³ The respondent argued that the various Decrees of the then Federal Military Government ousted the jurisdiction of the court while the trial court upheld the ouster clause. Both the Court of Appeal and the Supreme Court rejected the clause. The area that became source of worry was the court's decision per Pats Acholonu (JCA) when he posited that: "... by not merely adopting the African Charter but enacting it into our organic law, tenor and intendment of the preamble and section seem to vest that (i.e African Charter) with a greater vigor and strength than mere Decree for it has been elevated to a higher pedestal. "The question that readily comes to mind is by which court and by what law was it so elevated? The position adumbrated by Acholonu (JCA) was seriously criticized by the learned writer Babatunde, I. O.⁶⁴ the decision could not stand the test for a revisit of the decision by the Apex Court on this decision of utmost legal importance. Ogundare JSC varied the matter differently when he held that:

No doubt, cap 10 is a statute with international flavor. Being so, therefore, I would think that if there is a conflict between it and another statute, its provisions will prevail over those other statutes for the legislature does not intend to breach an international obligation. To this extent I agree with their lordships of the court below that the charter possesses a greater vigor and strength than any other domestic statute. But that is not to say that the charter is superior to the constitution.⁶⁵

This position of law is true in part and that is in respect of the supremacy of the Constitution which provides for its binding over all persons and authority throughout the federation and where there is a conflict between it and any other law, such law would be void.⁶⁶ The dissenting

62 (2000) FWLR (pt 4) p.533

63 Cap. A9 Laws of Federation of Nigeria, 2004.

64 Babatunde, I. O (2014) *Treaty Making and its Application under Nigerian Law: The Journey so far*, www.ijmi.org. Accessed on 12/2/2018

65 Emphasis added (2000) FWLR pt 4 p.533

66 S. 1 (1) of the Constitution

opinion of Achike JSC is however preferred to the view expressed by Ogundare JSC⁶⁷ He held that:

...the general rule is that a treaty which has been domesticated and incorporated into the body of the municipal laws ranks at par with the municipal laws. It is rather startling that a law passed to give effect to a treaty should stand on a higher pedestal above all other municipal laws, without more in the absence of any express provision in the law that incorporated the treaty into the municipal law.⁶⁸

The above views examined of the learned justices of the Court of Appeal and Supreme Court indicated that no matter how relevant the provision of a charter or treaty is in Nigeria, it cannot enjoy judicial enforceability unless it is domesticated and incorporated into municipal law.⁶⁹ And where same is done, it ranks higher than other municipal laws with the exception of the Constitution. The decisions of these courts no doubt are in accordance with Vienna convention on the law of treaties.⁷⁰

7.0 LEGALITY OF THE APPLICATION OF THE CHARTER ON DEMOCRACY IN NIGERIA

Considering the above Nigerian principles relating to international instruments, the provision of the Charter on Democracy, before its enactment into law, has no such force of law as to make its provisions justiciable before the Nigerian courts. In *Mhwun v. Minister of Health & Productivity & Ors*,⁷¹ the Court of Appeal held that the provisions of the International Labor Convention cannot be invoked and applied by a Nigerian court until same has been re-enacted by an act of the National Assembly. His Lordship, Muntaka Coomassie JCA (as he then was) had this to say on domestic application of International Labor Convention in Nigeria:

...there is no evidence before the court that ILO Convention, even though signed by the Nigerian government, has been enacted into law by the National Assembly. In so far as the ILO

67Babatunde, I. O (2014) Op. cit.

68Fawehinmi v. Abacha.(Supra). P.613

69 The Constitution uses word “shall” which connotes in Nigerian legislation means must or mandatory: *Kere v. Kalba* (2004) ALLF.WLR pt221. P1479

70Article 26 Vienner Convention; op cit.

71 (2005) 17 NWLR pt 953 p.120

Convention has not been enacted into law by the National Assembly it has no force of law in Nigeria and it cannot possibly apply...

Section 12 (2) of the Constitution provides that: “The National Assembly may make laws for the federation or any part thereof with respect to matters included in the Exclusive Legislative list for the purpose of implementing a treaty.” The intendment of this section is that the legislative competence of the states would be interfered with where the proposed legislation seeks to implement a treaty, and where there is a conflict between the position of the National Assembly and any State House of Assembly that bother on implementation of a treaty or any law whatsoever. Section 4 (5) of the Constitution empowers the federal law to prevail and that the state law to be void.⁷² The provision of section 12 (2) is however qualified by section 12 (3) which requires that “a bill for an Act of National Assembly passed pursuant to S.12 (2) shall not be presented to the president for assent unless it is ratified by a majority of all the Houses of Assembly in the federation.”⁷³ From the position of S. 12, implementation of treaties in Nigeria can be divided into two major headings. First are those that deal with matters in the exclusive legislative list governed by section 12 (1) and the other one that deals with concurrent legislative list governed by section 12 (2) and (3) of the Constitution.⁷⁴

In Nigeria, it can be authoritatively stated that treaties or charters are not part of the sources of Nigerian law. Nigeria follows the dualist theory for the implementation of international law at domestic level.⁷⁵ It requires the process of transformation which entails clothing them domestically by making them part of the statutes of the country, but does not entail subjecting treaties to the vicissitudes of municipal politics.⁷⁶ Transformation may be achieved through two methods: by re-enactment and by reference. The former is when the implementing statute directly enacts specific provisions or the entire treaty usually in the form of a schedule to the statute whereas the latter is usually contained either in the long and short titles of the statutes or in the preamble.⁷⁷

72 Babatunde, I. O (2014) *Treaty making and its Application Under Nigerian Law*. Op. cit

73 I bid

74 I bid

75 I bid

76 I bid

77 Ononrherhinor, F. A, (2016) *A Re-Examination of Treaties in Nigeria*. www.ajol.infor. Accessed on 13/2/2018

The African Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance falls under the categories of law making treaty which the Treaty (Making Procedures etc.) Act⁷⁸ requires its type to be enacted into law before it can be applicable in the Nigerian courts.⁷⁹ Nigeria has since 9th January, 2012 ratified the African Charter on Democracy, Election and Governance and hence she becomes a state party. The Charter on Democracy defines state party as “any member state of African Union which has ratified it and deposited the instrument for ratification with Chairperson of the African Union Commission.”⁸⁰ The Charter on Democracy also provides that: “The Charter shall enter into force thirty (30) days after the deposit of fifteen (15) instruments of Ratification.”⁸¹ This has been achieved in January 16, 2012 where Cameroon happened to be the fifteenth state to ratify the Charter on Democracy and therefore it came into force on 15th February, 2012.⁸²

Therefore, by ratification of the Charter on Democracy, Nigeria becomes bound by its provisions at International level. However, by the combined provisions of section 12 of the Constitution and the provisions of the Treaties (Making Procedures etc.) Act, since the provisions of the Charter on Democracy may change or alter the legislative powers same cannot be applicable and enforceable in Nigeria unless domesticated to be part of the domestic laws of the country. Despite the facts that it has not yet been domesticated in Nigeria⁸³, as it has been examined in this work, some of its provisions relating to elections can be found in the Constitution and other federal legislations like the Electoral Act 2022 etc.

8.0 CONCLUSION

In a democratic government, political parties facilitate governance by enabling citizens at the grass root level to play a role in policy making and they are also principal means for the representation of the electorate in both national and local government. A firm, strong and Independent electoral body is the key to successful democratic election. Good Governance is achieved in Democratic Government only where democratic elections are free, fair and transparent.

78 Cap T. 20 Vol. 15 LFN. 2004

79 S. 3 (1) a I bid

80 Article One of the Charter on Democracy

81 Article 48, Ibid

82 www.au.org. Accessed on 13/4/2018

83 Information obtained from Oral interview with HarunaEsq, Legal Department, National Assembly, Abuja. On 26/3/2018

8.1 THE PAPER HAS THE FOLLOWING FINDINGS:

- i. The Charter on Democracy provides provisions concerning democratic elections, the true adherence to which may bring peace and political stability to Africa.
- ii. The Independence of the Nigerian electoral body (INEC) is inchoate, because its funding comes from the President instead of consolidated revenue fund as it is the case with other independent bodies like the Judiciary. The appointment of the INEC Chairman and its Commissioners is vested in the President subject to confirmation by the senate which in some cases the procedure is abused where it is not done with due process. This is not in line with provision of the charter on democracy which requires each state party to have independent and impartial electoral body in its state.
- iii. In Nigeria, internal party democracy is lacking within political parties. It is delegates that vote during party convention and these delegates in most cases are compromised by wealthy members and most of them are not democratically selected or they represent their selfish interest rather than the party manifestation.
- iv. The Charter on Democracy which has been ratified in Nigeria has not yet been domesticated and therefore cannot have force of law. Even though, most of its provision can be found in the Constitution and other Nigerian legislations but non domestication of same makes it not possible to be applicable and enforceable in our domestic courts.

8.2 THE PAPER MAKES THE FOLLOWING RECOMMENDATIONS:

- i. State parties to the Charter on Democracy should ensure strict implementation of its provision in their periodic elections with the aim to provide peace, security and political stability in their respective states.
- ii. INEC should be strengthened to enable it fulfill its constitutional responsibilities in monitoring the activities of political parties. Political parties and Citizens must be ready to insist on and work for clean election campaigns. They should condemn anti-democratic practices such as vote buying, political godfatherism and election violence.
- iii. Independence of INEC should be a reality in the selection of its Chairman and members, if need be, civil society organizations should be included in their selection. Autonomy of its budget and the authority it exerts to enforce election laws and regulations should also be actualized. This should also extend to state and local governments electoral bodies. This will no doubt show the level of commitment to the obligations undertaken by Nigeria by signing and ratifying the Charter on Democracy.

- iv.** Finally, the Charter on Democracy which has been ratified in Nigeria since 2012, need to be implemented in order to get application and enforcement in Nigerian courts of justice. The AU Commission should device measures of sensitizing state parties to the Charter on Democracy to domesticate it so that they fully implement its provisions. Stakeholders and other people whose role is important in the management of democratic elections should do same.